

In vitro Antioxidant and Analgesic Properties of Methanolic Extracts of the Fruits of *Xylopiya aethiopica* on Formalin-Induced Nociception

O. A. Osukoya^{a,*}, A. Cheke^a, O. B Adewale^a, J. O. Awe^a, O. Olasehinde^b

^aDepartment of Chemical Sciences, Afe Babalola University, Ado-Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria

^bDepartment of Medical Biochemistry, Afe Babalola University, Ado-Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria

Abstract

Xylopiya aethiopica, negro pepper, is commonly used in traditional medicine to treat different kinds of diseases and infections. Methanolic extract of the fruit of *Xylopiya aethiopica* was evaluated for its antioxidant and analgesic properties. Qualitative and quantitative phytochemical screening of the extract was done according to standard procedures. Antioxidant potential was investigated using 2,2-diphenyl-1-picryl hydrazyl (DPPH) scavenging activity. Analgesic activity was carried out using formalin-induced paw licking test in albino rats at 100, 200 and 400 mg extract per kg body weight. Qualitative phytochemical screening revealed the presence of tannins, saponins, flavonoids, glycosides and steroids in the extract. The extract significantly inhibited DPPH scavenging activity with percentage inhibition of 147.35% as compared to ascorbic acid (147.15%) at concentration of 0.20 mg/mL. The methanolic fruit extract of *Xylopiya aethiopica* significantly reduced ($p < 0.05$) formalin-induced paw licking in both early and late phases, with 28.31 and 64.90% inhibition at 400 mg/kg, in rats in a dose-dependent manner. It can be concluded that methanolic fruit extract of *Xylopiya aethiopica* showed marked antioxidant potential which could be linked to its ability to reduce formalin-induced paw licking. The fruits of *X. aethiopica* could, therefore, be suggested for use as an analgesic.

© NJEH 2019 Published by LivingScience Foundation.

Keywords: Anodyne, antinociceptive, antioxidant, Ethiopian pepper, pain reliever.

1. Introduction

Plants have been shown to possess various medicinal properties and have been used in curing/treating ailments affecting both humans and animals, due to the presence of bioactive constituents (Sukirtha and Growther, 2012). A number of chemical substances such as morphine, quinine and alkaloids have been synthesized from medicinal plants, thereby aiding medical practice (Ameyaw and Duker-Eshun, 2009; Fabricant and Farnsworth, 2001; Sukirtha and Growther, 2012).

Received 4 April 2019; Accepted 25 June 2019.

*Corresponding author

Email address: kemi210@yahoo.com (O. A. Osukoya)

Extracts from medicinal plants have been used by herbalists in the treatment of several human diseases for centuries, although with little or no scientific knowledge on the efficacy of the extracts. There is therefore a need for scientific data to assert the use of plants in traditional medicine. Also, there are many secondary effects linked to allopathic medicines, which may lead to other ailment/illness. To combat these side effects, medicinal herbs are used to prevent and cure diseases (Deshpande, 2006).

Xylopiya aethiopyca is commonly known as Ethiopia or Negro pepper, and belongs to the Annonaceae family. The plant is widely distributed in some parts of West and East Africa (Orwa *et al.*, 2009). In traditional medicine, fruits of *X. aethiopyca* are used for the treatment of malaria, fibroid, fungal infection, syphilis, rheumatism, boils, haemorrhoids, flatulence, bronchitis, hypertension, diabetes, dysentery (Iwu *et al.*, 1992; Johnkennedy *et al.*, 2011; Sofowora, 1996) and female infertility (Igwe *et al.*, 2003; Tatsadjieu *et al.*, 2003). *Xylopiya aethiopyca* is also used to sedate, and as an analgesic and laxative. The fine powder of its fruit mixed with Shea butter and coconut oil is used as cosmetics (Tatsadjieu *et al.*, 2003). The dried fruits are also used as flavourings for soups in West Africa.

The crushed seeds are applied topically on the forehead to treat headache and neuralgia. The seeds are also taken as decoction, concoction or chewed and swallowed in the treatment of haemorrhoids' numbness, epilepsy and anaemia. The leaves are used to treat dyspepsia, laryngitis, splenomegaly and headache (Igwe *et al.*, 2003). The stem bark is used for dysentery and female infertility. The stem could be used as firewood and is important in timber/carpentry industry (Orwa *et al.*, 2009; Tatsadjieu *et al.*, 2003). The odoriferous roots of *X. aethiopyca* are used in tinctures and the extract of the roots is used as an anthelmintic (Asekun and Adeniyi, 2004; Orwa *et al.*, 2009). *Xylopiya aethiopyca* fruits reportedly act as antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, nephroprotective, hypolipidemic, and hypoglycemic agent (Adewale *et al.*, 2015), which can be linked to the presence of phytochemicals. In light of these, methanolic extract of the fruits of *Xylopiya aethiopyca* were screened to ascertain the antioxidant activity and investigate its antinociceptive properties against formalin-induced pain in rats.

2. Materials and Methods

Plant collection and extraction

The dried fruits of *Xylopiya aethiopyca* were purchased from Koko Market, Koko, Delta State, Nigeria. The plant part was identified at the Department of Plant Science, Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria, and a specimen sample was deposited at the departmental herbarium for future reference. The fruits were opened to remove seeds, the dried fruits were blended into fine powder and macerated in 70% methanol for 24 h. The filtrate was concentrated using a rotary evaporator and dried using a water bath at 45 °C to obtain powdered concentrate.

Collection of experimental animalsd extraction

Thirty male Albino rats were purchased from the animal house, Afe Babalola University, Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria. The rats were fed with pelletized feed and water *ad libitum*. Animal experiment was conducted in accordance with the Animal Ethics Committee of Afe Babalola University, Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria.

Phytochemical screening and antioxidant Assay

Qualitative phytochemical screening was done using the standard procedures of Ghagane *et al.* (2017). Major constituents analysed were tannins, saponins, flavonoids and glycosides.

Determination of total phenolic content

The total phenolic content of the extract was determined by the method of Vermerris and Nicholson (2007). A 0.1 mL extract (10 mg/mL) was mixed with 2 mL of freshly prepared sodium carbonate (2%) and mixed vigorously. After 5 min, 100 µL Folin-Ciocalteu reagent (1 N) was added to the mixture and incubated for 30 min at room temperature. Absorbance at 750 nm was taken against blank. Gallic acid was used as the standard phenol at varying concentrations (0.04, 0.08, 0.16, 0.2 mg/mL) and the results were expressed as mg gallic acid equivalent per gram dry extract (mg GAE/g).

Determination of total flavonoid content

A solution of 5% NaNO₂ (0.3 mL) and 10% AlCl₃ (0.3 mL) in distilled water was added to 1 mL of extract, and incubated for 5 min. After, 2 mL of 1 M NaOH and 2.4 mL distilled water was added to get a final volume of 10 mL. Absorbance was measured at 510 nm. The total flavonoid content was expressed as mg rutin equivalents per gram dry extract (mgRE/g).

Determination of free radical scavenging ability

DPPH (1, 1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl) radical scavenging ability of *X. aethiopica* fruit methanolic extract was determined using the method described by Gyamfi *et al.* (1999). Extract (0.1 mL, 10 mg/mL) was mixed with 1 mL of 0.4 mM DPPH in methanolic solution and left in the dark for 30 min before taking the absorbance at 516 nm.

Nociceptive assay

Formalin-induced nociception

The formalin test was carried out as described by Mensah and Amoh—Barimah (2009) with slight modifications. The animals were divided into five groups of 3 rats each. Animals were fasted for 24 h before administration (*p.o*) but allowed access to water. The groups were denoted as group A - control (orally administered with 0.2 mL normal saline), group B - positive control (intraperitoneally injected with 100 mg/kg diclofenac Na), test group C (orally treated with 0.2 mL of 100 mg/kg methanolic extract of *Xylopiya aethiopica* fruits), test group D (orally administered with 0.2 mL of 200 mg/kg methanolic extract of *Xylopiya aethiopica* fruits) and test group E (orally treated with 0.2 mL of 400 mg/kg methanolic extract of *Xylopiya aethiopica* fruits). Thirty minutes after administration of saline and extracts, 50 µL formalin (2.5%) made up in phosphate buffered saline, pH 7.2, was injected subcutaneously under the dorsal surface of the right hind paw of all the animals. The number of times spent by each animal in licking the injected paw was observed and considered as an indication of pain. Early phase nociceptive response normally peaks 5 minutes after injection and late phase response peaks 15 – 30 minutes after formalin administration. The mean licking time of test groups was determined and compared with the mean for the control group. The experiment was conducted without any disturbance that may affect animals' response. Percentage inhibition was determined by comparing the results of extract with control group using the following formula:

$$\text{Percentage inhibition} = (A - T) / A \times 100,$$

where A is the average number of times spent licking paw of control and T is the average number of times spent licking paw of test group.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was done with the aid of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). Data were presented as mean ± SEM; data obtained was analyzed statistically by one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's posthoc test. *P* values less than 5% were considered statistically significant (*p* < 0.05).

3. Results and Discussion

Presence of phytochemicals

Phytochemicals such as tannins, saponins, flavonoids, steroids and glycosides were present in the methanolic extract of the fruits of *X. aethiopica*. However, terpenoids were absent, as shown in Table 1.

The total flavonoid and total phenolic contents of the extracts were 22.185±0.983 mgQE/g of dry plant material and 73.149±0.479 mg GAE/g, respectively.

Table 1: Phytochemical analysis of methanolic extract of the fruits of *Xylopi aethiopica*

Phytochemical	Status
Tannins	+
Saponins	+
Flavonoids	+
Terpenoids	-
Glycosides	+
Steroids	+

Legend:

+ indicates present and – indicates absence

Antioxidant ability

The result of DPPH scavenging activity (Figure 1) in this study indicated that the methanolic extract of *X. aethiopica* fruits have DPPH scavenging percentage inhibition of 147.35% when compared to ascorbic acid which showed 147.15 percent inhibition at concentration of 0.20 mg/mL.

Figure 1: DPPH scavenging ability of the methanolic fruit extract of *Xylopi aethiopica*.

Table 2: Antinociceptive effect of methanolic extract of the fruits of *Xylopi aethiopia* in formalin induced paw licking test

GROUP	DOSE (mg/kg)	Early phase response (0 - 5min post-formalin injection)		Late phase response (15 - 45 min post-formalin injection)	
		No of paw licking	Percent inhibition	No of paw licking	Percent inhibition
A (control)	Vehicle	29.50±3.50	-	111.12±1.50	-
B (Drug)	100	23.00±4.00	22.03	57.00±10.00 ^a	48.70
C (extract)	100	28.30±9.17	4.07	53.00±4.51 ^a	52.30
D (extract)	200	22.00±1.76	25.42	43.00±2.31 ^a	61.30
E (extract)	400	21.15±2.62	28.31	39.00±1.53 ^a	64.90

Results were expressed as mean±SEM (n = 3). Significant difference ^ap < 0.05 when compared to the control.

Antinociceptive activity

The results obtained indicated that the extract possessed antinociceptive abilities. Compared to the standard (diclofenac Na) used, the rats administered with the methanolic fruit extract of *Xylopi aethiopia* showed significant improvement in a dose dependent manner by reduction in number of licks in formalin-induced paw licking treated groups when compared with control (Table 2). The highest reduction was observed at 400 mg/kg extract. Interestingly, during the late phase response, the extract was most potent than the standard drug, diclofenac Na, even at the lowest dose of 100 mg/kg.

Discussion

The fruits of *Xylopi aethiopia* which is generally used for nutritive purposes in the making of soup was evaluated for antioxidant and antinociceptive activity in rats. The fruit extract contained certain phytochemicals, such as saponins, tannins and steroids, which are characterised with antinociceptive qualities (Ayedoun *et al.*, 1996).

Antioxidants generally exert their activity through different mechanisms such as chelation of ferrous ion, degradation of peroxide and scavenging of free radicals (Le *et al.*, 2007). The *in vitro* antioxidant assay performed on this plant revealed significant antioxidant potential. *Xylopi aethiopia* was shown to reduce DPPH scavenging ability, as DPPH free radical scavenging method is usually used to investigate the scavenging activity of many natural extracts and compounds (Liu and Ng, 2000). The reduction of DPPH scavenging ability is a promising strategy to curing various diseases of oxidative stress, tissue degenerative diseases, and even cancer. It has been reported that phenolic compounds present in plants are associated with antioxidant activities or termination of free radicals actions, and that they play important role in preventing lipid peroxidation (Shajiselvin and Muthu, 2010). The presence of hydroxyl ion on phenols are responsible for the radical scavenging effect primarily as a result of its redox properties (Rice-Evans *et al.*, 1997). The methanolic extract of *Xylopi aethiopia* contained considerable amounts of total phenols as reported in this study. The aqueous extract of *X. aethiopia* has also been shown to contain high contents of phenolics and volatile compounds which acts as strong natural antioxidants (Abd-Algader *et al.*, 2013).

The extract significantly reduced formalin-induced hind paw licking, and this was verified by comparing the number of licks of the test groups with the rat group administered with the standard drug. The formalin-induced paw licking test is a valid model of clinical pain, mostly predicting acute pain. It produces two phases of nociceptive response usually due to direct stimulation of nociceptors in the paw which results in centrally mediated pain, the first known as the neurogenic phase occurs as a result of direct stimulation of C-fibre nociceptors by the injected formalin. The second, (the inflammatory phase) occurs as a result of the combinatory effect of an inflammatory reaction in the peripheral tissue and changes in central processing (Tjølsen *et al.*, 1992).

Phytochemicals such as flavonoids and phenolic compounds, mainly from plants, have been reported to play an important role in inflammatory reactions, thereby acting as anti-inflammatory agents (Arulselvan *et al.*, 2016). In this study, methanolic extract of *Xylopia aethiopica* inhibited both phases of formalin-induced nociception, which could be linked to high total phenolic and flavonoid contents. It could be suggested that its action is central like opioids.

4. Conclusion

The methanolic extract of *Xylopia aethiopica* is suitable for use, especially in pharmacological products, as an anodyne for treatment of pain, which could be due to its antioxidant properties.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank all technologists in Department of Chemical Sciences, Afe Babalola University for their assistance during the course of this work.

Statement of Ethics

The procedures followed for the care of the animals used for this study were according to the standards in the National Institutes of Health guide for the care and use of Laboratory animals (NIH Publications No. 8023, revised 1978), as approved by the Animal Ethics Committee of Afe Babalola University, Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria.

Disclosure Statement

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

Funding Sources

This research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

References

- Abd-Algader, N.N., El-Kamali, H.H., Ramadan, M.M., Ghanem, K.Z. and Farrag, A., 2013. *Xylopia aethiopica* volatile compounds protect against panadol-induced hepatic and renal toxicity in male rats. *World Applied Sciences Journal* **27**, 10-22.
- Adewale, O.B. and Orhue, N.E.J., 2015. Protective effect of aqueous extract of *Xylopia aethiopica* fruits on carbon tetrachloride-induced nephrotoxicity in rats. *Journal of Experimental and Integrative Medicine* **5**, 105-109.
- Ameyaw, Y. and Duker-Eshun, G., 2009. The alkaloid contents of the ethno-plant organs of three antimalarial medicinal plant species in the eastern region of Ghana. *International Journal of Chemical Sciences* **7**, 48-58.
- Arulselvan, P., Fard, M.T., Tan, W.S., Gothai, S., Fakurazi, S., Norhaizan, M. E. and Kumar, S. S., 2016. Role of Antioxidants and Natural Products in Inflammation. *Oxidative Medicine and Cellular Longevity*, 5276130.
- Asekun, O. and Adeniyi, B., 2004. Antimicrobial and cytotoxic activities of the fruit essential oil of *Xylopia aethiopica* from Nigeria. *Fitoterapia* **75**, 368-370.
- Ayedoun, A., Adeoti, B., Sossou, P. and Leclercq, P.A., 1996. Influence of fruit conservation methods on the essential oil composition of *Xylopia aethiopica* (Dunal) A. Richard from Benin. *Flavour and Fragrance Journal* **11**, 245-250.
- Deshpande, D., 2006. A Source Book of Herbal Remedies (Chemical constituents, Biological activities and Usage). A Handbook of Medicinal herbs. Chopsal Road, Jodhpur, India: AGROBIOS, 2006:267-268.
- Fabricant, D.S. and Farnsworth, N.R., 2001. The value of plants used in traditional medicine for drug discovery. *Environmental Health Perspectives* **109**, 69-75.
- Ghagane, S.C., Puranik, S.I., Kumbar, V.M., Nerli, R.B., Jalalpure, S.S., Hiremath, M.B., Neelagund, S. and Aladakatti, R., 2017. In vitro antioxidant and anticancer activity of *Leea indica* leaf extracts on human prostate cancer cell lines. *Integrative Medicine Research* **6**, 79-87.
- Gyamfi, M.A., Yonamine, M. and Aniya, Y., 1999. Free-radical scavenging action of medicinal herbs from Ghana: *Thonningia sanguinea* on experimentally-induced liver injuries. *General Pharmacology: The Vascular System* **32**, 661-667.
- Igwe, S., Afonne, J. and Ghasi, S., 2003. Ocular dynamics of systemic aqueous extracts of *Xylopia aethiopica* (African guinea pepper) seeds on visually active volunteers. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology* **86**, 139-142.
- Iwu, M.M., Jackson, J.E., Tally, J.D. and Klayman, D.L., 1992. Evaluation of plant extracts for antileishmanial activity using a mechanism-based radiorespirometric microtechnique (RAM). *Planta Medica* **58**, 436-341.
- Johnkennedy, N., Adamma, E., Austin, A. and Chukwunyeri, N., 2011. Influence of *Xylopia aethiopica* fruits on some hematological and biochemical profile. *The American Journal of the Medical Sciences* **4**, 191-196.
- Le, K., Chiu, F. and Ng, K., 2007. Identification and quantification of antioxidants in *Fructus lycii*. *Food Chemistry* **105**, 353-363.
- Liu, F. and Ng, T., 2000. Antioxidative and free radical scavenging activities of selected medicinal herbs. *Life Sciences* **66**, 725-735.
- Mensah, T. and Amoh—Barimah, A., 2009. An Evaluation of the Anti-inflammatory, Antipyretic and Antinociceptive Effects of *Ficus exasperata* (Vahl) Leaf Extract. *Journal of Pharmacology and Toxicology* **4**, 138-151.

- Orwa, C., Mutua, A., Kindt, R., Jamnadass, R. and Anthony, S., 2009. Agroforestry Database: a tree reference and selection guide version 4.0. World Agroforestry Centre, Kenya 15.
- Rice-Evans, C., Miller, N. and Paganga, G., 1997. Antioxidant properties of phenolic compounds. *Trends in Plant Science* **2**, 152-159.
- Shajiselvin, C. and Muthu, A.K., 2010. In-vitro antioxidant studies of various extracts of whole plant of *Borreria hispida* (Linn). *Research Journal of Pharmaceutical Biological and Chemical Sciences* **1**, 14-20.
- Sofowora, A., 1996. Medicinal Plants and Traditional Medicine in Africa. Karthala, Paris, France.
- Sukirtha, K. and Growther, L., 2012. Antibacterial, antifungal and phytochemical analysis of selected medicinal plants. *Journal of Natural Products and Plant Resources* **2**, 644-648.
- Tatsadjieu, L., Ngang, J.E., Ngassoum, M. and Etoa, F.-X., 2003. Antibacterial and antifungal activity of *Xylopiya aethiopica*, *Monodora myristica*, *Zanthoxylum xanthoxylodes* and *Zanthoxylum leprieurii* from Cameroon. *Fitoterapia* **74**, 469-472.
- Tjølsen, A., Berge, O.-G., Hunskaar, S., Rosland, J.H. and Hole, K., 1992. The formalin test: an evaluation of the method. *Pain* **51**, 5-17.
- Vermeris, W. and Nicholson, R., 2008. Isolation and identification of phenolic compounds. In Phenolic Compound Biochemistry. Springer, Dordrecht, 151-196